

MACROSCOPIC EXAMINATION OF THE COMMON SELF-HEAL (*PRUNELLA VULGARIS* L.)

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Relevance: Common self-heal (*Prunella vulgaris* L.) is a promising medicinal plant used in folk medicine as an anti-inflammatory, antihistamine, antibacterial, and antifungal agent. In light of the growing interest in herbal preparations, the study of morphological characteristics of the above-ground parts of this species growing in the Republic of Uzbekistan is of particular importance.

The purpose of this study is to study the macroscopic morphological features of the above-ground part of common self-heal growing in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods: The object of the research work was the herb of medicinal self-heal. The raw materials were harvested in June-July 2022 in natural areas around the Chimgan district, following generally accepted rules for harvesting, primary processing, drying, and storage of medicinal plant raw materials. The analysis included visual study of the external morphological characteristics of raw materials: shape, size, color, stem texture, and leaves. Macroscopic examination was conducted in accordance with the methodological recommendations of the State Pharmacopoeia of the Republic of Uzbekistan (I-edition).

Fig. 1. Raw materials of the common self-heal (*Prunella vulgaris* L.): A - whole raw material, B - leaf, C - flower. **Designations** - A: 1 - petiole; 2 - leaf plate; 3 - flower.

Results and Discussions: Morphological analysis of whole leaves, flowers, and stem of common blackthorn showed that the size of the studied leaves ranged from 4 to 7 cm (Figures 1 and 2). Leaves are simple, petiolate, oblong-ovate or lanceolate, with a wedge-shaped base and a blunt apex. Upper leaves sessile, serrated. The stem is quadrangular, ascending, reddish, glabrous in the lower part, scattered-pilose along the ribs in the middle, and whitish-hairy at the apex. The flowers are small, ranging from red-violet to dark-violet, and are gathered in dense, spike-like or capitate inflorescences. Flowers on short pedicels in false whorls 2-4 cm long, bisexual, sometimes with underdeveloped pollen.

Conclusions: Macroscopic examination of the above-ground part of common bunt (*Prunella vulgaris* L.) made it possible to identify diagnostic features important for the pharmacognostic identification of raw materials. The obtained data can be used in the development of quality standards for medicinal plant raw materials.